

Earthquake Behavior of Historic Timber-Masonry of Lefkas Ionian Island, Greece

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Abstract-This paper deals with the earthquake response of the historic traditional buildings of Lefkas Island, Greece. These structures have up to four storeys and are located in the central area of the Lefkas town. The main characteristic of these buildings is their dual bearing system, which consists of a spatial timber multi-storey system and a single-storey masonry wall system, respectively. The multi-storey wooden system possesses in elevation various diagonal trusses infilled by bricks with lime mortar. The top of the building is spatially connected by means of a tiled wooden truss roof. During the strong earthquake at Lefkas Island (August 14, 2003) the earthquake behavior of the above-mentioned buildings was very good. Only damages that could be repaired (without total collapse) were observed, e.g. partial collapse of masonry walls at ground floor, various cracks in the vicinity of masonry openings. In the timber multi-storey frames many bricks cracked and fell out of plane, but otherwise no significant damage was observed. In this paper, an analytical investigation of the earthquake response of such historical buildings has taken place, in order to explain their seismic damage due to the above-mentioned strong earthquake.

Keywords-Lefkas Earthquake; Traditional Buildings; Structural Damages; Buildings with Dual Structural System

I. INTRODUCTION

On August 14, 2003 at 05:15 GMT, a strong earthquake of magnitude $M=6.2$ occurred in the Greek Ionian Sea, very close to the Lefkas Island. The strong motion of this earthquake was recorded by many accelerographs of the Institute of Engineering Seismology and Earthquake Engineering (ITSAK) network. The peaks of the three seismic components were 0.42g and 0.34g for the two horizontal directions and 0.19g for the vertical one, while the strong motion duration was 18s. The traditional building category (Figs.1, 2) examined in this article represents 34% of the total building stock of the town, is encountered in the historical centre and has been discussed in the past (Touliatos, 2000; Makarios & Demosthenous 2006; Vintzileou *et al* 2007; Karakostas *et al* 2005). The architectural morphology, the construction materials of these structures, the very interesting dual structural bearing system, as well as the observed damages from previous strong earthquakes have already been dealt with in the past. In the present paper interesting numerical results by a further extended parametric analysis, which have been applied in the past to similar traditional buildings with dual structural system, are given.

Fig. 1 Traditional building with dual bearing system

Fig. 2 Typical external view of a such traditional building

It is worth noting that the traditional buildings at Lefkas town have up to four storeys and have a dual load carrying

system, a wooden multistory 3D-frame and a stone masonry single-storey wall that envelopes and connects (on the ground floor) the wooden system (Figs.3-7).

Fig. 3 The concept of the dual bearing system of the traditional buildings

Fig. 4 The wooden 3D frame of the upper storey

Fig. 5 Details of the wooden frame of the upper storey

On the upper floors the wooden 3D frame possesses diagonal wooden trusses. Single-layer brick masonry walls with lime mortar fill the wooden trusses. The majority of these buildings are residential houses and the rest of them are public buildings, such as schools, the old town hall, etc. Despite the age of these buildings (many of which were built more than 200 years ago), almost all of them are in use nowadays. It is noted that poor soil conditions and the high level of underground water characterize the center of the Lefkas town. Therefore the traditional builders applied a specific type (Fig.8) of foundation in these buildings that

consists of a sub-foundation of horizontally placed tree trunks in three levels (Makarios & Demosthenous, 2006; Vintzileou et al, 2007), while this sub-foundation resembles approximately an ancient (primitive) seismic base isolation system (the first case of seismic isolation system in the world) without ditch in the perimeter of the building (Makarios & Demosthenous, 2006).

Fig. 6 Details of the infill wooden frame with brick masonry

Fig. 7 Details of the wooden joint elements

Fig. 8 The foundation form of these buildings

II. EARTHQUAKE DAMAGE – NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION - RESULTS

The structural damages of the traditional buildings observed after the earthquake can be classified in the following categories: (a) Damage on the tiled of roofs due to vertical seismic component; (b) Damage in the stone masonry walls at the ground floor, which included cracking

of masonry units (stones) or at the joint of mortar, and partial collapse of masonry walls (Fig.9); (c) Damage on the wooden frames with brick masonry infills in the upper storeys (Fig.10).

Fig. 9 Local partial failure of masonry walls at the ground floor

Fig. 10 Out-of-plane collapse of masonry infill

Fig. 11 An open view of the 3D finite element numerical model

In this work, an analytical investigation of the seismic behaviour of the traditional buildings discussed is performed in order to explain the observed damages and interpret the causes of failure. Modeling of the masonry walls of the ground floor has been performed by suitable shell finite elements. Different shell finite elements have been used for the infill masonry walls of the upper floors, while for modeling of the wooden frames beam elements are used. Also, suitable failure criteria for masonry walls have been adopted. The recorded time histories of the acceleration along the two horizontal directions at the center of Lefkas town have been used as base excitation (Margaris *et al* 2003) in the analyses.

Fig. 12 Horizontal displacements due to Lefkas Earthquake

Fig. 13 Distribution of stresses s22(vertical) and s11(horizontal) due to Lefkas earthquake

The numerical results of representative numerical models of two/three-story traditional buildings are presented and discussed in the following. From the in-situ investigation in Lefkas town the special characteristics (dimensions, used materials, type and strength of masonries, existed conditions etc) of the traditional buildings have been recorded (Makarios & Demosthenous, 2006). Analyses have been carried out through SAP2000, v15.1, (Figs.11-13). As it may be seen in Fig.12 the maximum displacement response occurred at mid-height of the upper storey due to the out-of-plane response. The distribution of the out-of-plane response in terms of stresses of the model at different time steps during base excitation is shown in Fig.13. As it is shown in this figure and according to the conclusions from the modal analysis of the examined model the out-of-plane response of the upper floors is governed by the local modes

(Makarios and Demosthenous, 2006). The time histories of the displacement response of the two different positions (at midheight and at the end of the upper floor) are showed in Fig.14.

Fig. 14 Displacements at mid-height and at the end of the upper storey

III. FAILURE CRITERIA OF MASONRY STRUCTURES

In Fig. 13 the envelopes of the tensile stresses in two principal directions (s11 and s22) are presented. Tensile stress concentrations are observed in midheight of the infill walls of the upper floor agreeing with the positions of the observed damages from the in-situ observations. Furthermore, wooden frames remain in the elastic range and therefore they are not expected to suffer any structural damage, a fact also confirmed from in-situ observations. It has been mentioned that structural damages in this type of buildings were mainly observed in the stone masonry walls at the ground floor and in the brick masonry infills in the upper stories. The failure criterion of Von-Misses is being used for the masonry walls, because it is considered to be the most suitable for this case. The parameters needed for the definition of the surface shown in Fig.(15) are the compression strength $f_c=4000 \text{ kN/m}^2$ and the tension ultimate strength $f_t=400 \text{ kN/m}^2$, namely f_t was assumed equal to $0.10f_c$. Cracking of masonry in both stress directions (s11 and s22) occurs when the state of stress is of the biaxial tension-tension type and both tensile principal stresses are beyond the tensile -failure envelope, which is designated as zone z1 in Fig.15. In this case the material loses its tensile strength completely. The stress state in two directions from time history analyses in various locations has been compared to the assumed failure envelope. A more thorough investigation about the types of failure can be found elsewhere (Makarios & Demosthenous, 2006). A major conclusion is that cracking of the masonry walls at the first floor and crushing of the masonry infill in the upper story may occur in case of masonry with small values of compressive strength, which in fact is in good agreement with the in-situ observations. On the other hand, shear failure at the interfaces of masonry infills and wooden elements (Fig.16) of the upper storey may occur for masonry with higher tensile strength as the one assumed in this paper. It is clear that in case such a failure occurs (tensile or shear) the resistance of the masonry walls in the out-of-plane response is reduced and out-of-plane collapse is prone to happen, as it was actually observed at the earthquake of Lefkas island.

Fig. 15 Stress state of the more stressed area at the stone-masonry walls of the first storey

Fig. 16 Stress state of brick-masonry infill at the corner of wooden elements at the upper storey

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The local bearing system of the traditional buildings of Lefkas Island was systematically investigated and the following conclusions have been arising.

First, the traditional buildings with a dual structural system behaved very well despite the long strong duration (about 18s, *Margaris et al, 2013*) of the Lefkas earthquake (August 14th, 2003) and the high peak ground accelerations values (0.42g & 0.36g for the two seismic components, respectively).

Furthermore, the structural damages in the traditional buildings observed after the Lefkas earthquake can be classified into two main categories related to the structural system: Cracking and partial collapse of the ground floor stone masonry walls (in several cases) and shear failure, crushing and out of plane collapse of the upper stories brick masonry infills (in many cases). The timber frame, both in the ground and in the upper floor did not suffer any damage. In addition and instead of serious damages have been observed in modern structures and especially to infrastructures by foundation settlements, no one case of such damages have been observed in the traditional buildings, despite the poor soil conditions at the old town district of Lefkas, where the majority of such type of buildings is existed. Neither damage in the infrastructure nor foundation settlements were observed in the traditional buildings at the old town district of Lefkas, despite the poor soil conditions, as opposed to what happened in modern structures many of which suffered serious damages. The comparatively improved seismic behaviour of the traditional buildings may

be attributed to the use of extended wooden footings at three levels.

Moreover, it has been typically observed that damage in the brick masonry infills of the upper floors systematically concentrated around the middle of the storey height and were usually accompanied by out-of-plane collapse.

It is worth noting that, according to the results of the numerical investigation the maximum displacements and tensile stresses were concentrated around the middle of the height of the upper stories. This is in agreement with the in-situ observations.

Following the previous point, comparing the numerical results of the state of stress with an adopted simple failure criterion that is based on stresses in two principal directions, the following important findings have been underlined: By applying a simple failure criterion to the stresses along two principal directions which resulted from the analysis, the following interesting conclusion was deduced: Cracking at the stone masonry walls of the ground floor and crushing at the brick masonry infills of the upper stories can develop in case of masonry with small values of compressive strength. This is a good verification and explanation of the in-situ observations.

Finally, the single story stone-masonry 3D-system (the first bearing system) has uncoupling fundamental period about 0.015 to 0.02s for fixed foundation, while the wooden multistory 3D-system (the second bearing system) has uncoupling fundamental period about 0.20 to 0.23s for fixed foundation, namely the difference is of 1st order of magnitude. In addition, the two mode shapes of the first bearing system are characterized as global mode shapes, while the first two mode shapes of the second bearing system are characterized as local mode shapes (vibration of infilled walls out of the their plane). The coupling of the two bearing systems is a very smart idea and an important issue that has been applied by the technicians and expert builders of Lefkas Island in the last 200 years. It provides the traditional building with multiplex lines of reserve capacity during earthquake events as it has been proved by the observed damage which mainly were concentrated in the secondary elements, i.e the infill walls.

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